

Time Dependent Schrodinger Equation and Variance of Conditional Momentum

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 11, 2019

In this note, we wish to examine how the variance of $u(x) = \frac{\sum_p p f_p \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)}$ namely: $P(x)$ Conditional Variance(p) changes as one moves from one point to another. If one tries to eliminate $u(x)$ from the first order change, one obtains $d/dx P(x) = 2 u(x) P(x)$ which is a quantum mechanical result. This also leads to the change in the variance depending only on the force and kinetic energy. $d/dx P(x) = 2 u(x) P(x)$ also dictates how Shannon's spatial entropy changes from point to point. Thus, it seems that the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be thought of in terms of changes in entropy density. The ideas here are a little different from those of (1).

Conditional Probability

Consider a quantum particle in a potential to be modeled by $\exp(ipx)$. This "wave type" object is scattered frequently by the potential $V(x)$ into different p states, e.g. $\exp(ip_1 x)$, $\exp(ip_2 x)$ etc. These have different weights f_p . If one uses conditional probability, one may suggest:

$$u(x) = \langle p \rangle = \frac{\sum_p p f_p \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)} \quad ((1))$$

$u(x)$ is an average momentum, assuming the particle is at x . Let us call $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$. This normalization factor is the wavefunction, but it seems that one does not need to be aware of this. One may only think in terms of $\langle p \rangle$, $\langle p^2 \rangle$ and $P(x)$.

$$\text{Conditional Var}(p) = \sum_p p^2 P(p/x) - [\sum_p p P(p/x)]^2 \quad ((2))$$

This should be related to average kinetic energy as $\langle p^2 \rangle$ is very similar to kinetic energy.

$$\text{Note: } d/dx u(x) = -\sum_p p^2 P(p/x) - [\sum_p p P(p/x)]^2$$

Consider next

$$P(x) \text{ Conditional Var} \quad ((3))$$

The first order change as one moves from x to $x+b$ is:

$$d/dx [P(x) \text{ Conditional Var}(p)] = [d/dx P(x)] [\text{Conditional Var}] + P(x) d/dx \text{ Conditional Var}(p)$$

or

$$[d/dx P(x)] [\langle p^*p \rangle - u(x)u(x)] + P(x) d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle - P(x) 2 u(x) d/dx u(x) \quad ((4))$$

Assume $d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle$ is related to $d/dx v(x)v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity given by:

$$.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E. \text{ In such a case, } P(x) d/dx [v(x)v(x)] \text{ is related to } P(x)\text{Force}(x).$$

If one wants to eliminate $u(x)$, then one must consider

$$-[d/dx P(x)] u(x)u(x) - 2u(x) P(x) d/dx u(x) = -[d/dx P(x)] u(x)u(x) - 2 u(x) P(x) [- \langle p^*p \rangle - u(x)u(x)] \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{If } d/dx P(x) - 2 P(x) u(x) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Then ((5)) reduces to $2 u(x) P(x) \langle p^*p \rangle$. There is still a $u(x)$ in this equation, but $2 u(x) P(x)$ can be changed to $d/dx P(x)$. Then the change is:

$$[d/dx P(x)] \langle p^*p \rangle + P(x) d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle + [d/dx P(x)] \langle p^*p \rangle = P(x) d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle + 2 \langle p^*p \rangle d/dx P(x)$$

Here $\langle p^*p \rangle$ is the conditional variance of p .

This suggests the first order change in $P(x)[\langle p^*p \rangle - u(x)u(x)]$ is proportional to $\text{Force}(x)P(x) + \text{constant kinetic energy } d/dx P(x)$.

In a note (2), we discussed this by taking the derivative of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Alternatively, one may consider calculating:

$d/dx [P(x) d/dx u(x)]$ Here $d/dx u(x)$ is the change in the conditional momentum with respect to x .

Then:

$$d/dx P(x) d/dx u(x) + P(x) d/dx d/dx u(x) = d/dx P(x) [-\langle p^*p \rangle - u(x)u(x)] + P(x) [-d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle - 2u(x) d/dx u(x)]$$

Eliminating dependence on $u(x)$ gives:

$$- u(x)u(x) d/dx P(x) + P 2 u(x)u(x)u(x)=0 \text{ or } ((6)) \text{ again which is a quantum result.}$$

Then:

$d/dx [P(x) d/dx u(x)] = - P(x) d/dx \langle p^*p \rangle$ which is equivalent to $P(x) \text{Force}(x)$

It should be noted that ((6)) is related to changes in entropy as it may be rewritten as:

$$- d/dx s(x) = - 2u(x) s(x) + 2 P(x) u(x) \quad ((8))$$

Where $s(x)$ is Shannon's spatial entropy density given by $s(x) = - P(x) \ln[P(x)]$.

Thus, ((6)) suggests that Shannon's spatial entropy changes in x in a certain way to ensure that ((5)) is satisfied.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to obtain the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, by making use of both $P(x)$ and $P(p/x)$. We find that in quantum mechanics there is an average momentum at x given by $u(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p \text{ fp } \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p \text{ fp } \exp(ipx)]$. We calculate the change in this variance multiplied by $P(x)$. If one wants to eliminate all reference to $u(x)$, one obtains $dP(x)/dx = 2u(x) P(x)$. The equation in the line above also dictates how Shannon's spatial entropy density changes as one moves from one point to another.

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Schrodinger Equation in Terms of Flux (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fluxes in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2019)